

gall midge severely attacked the second crop of rice about 80 km east of Bangkok, in Bangkhanarg village, Bangnampriew district, Chachengsao province. A survey was conducted in the village in June and July.

Rice is irrigated throughout the year. A second crop of about 480 ha of high yielding varieties (mostly RD) has been directly sown during March and April since 1976. The insecticides carbofuran

3G and monocrotophos 50% E.C. were applied at about 45 and 60 days after sowing, but they were not effective because the application was late. Precipitation was 5.5 mm in March, 54.7 mm in April, and 121.0 mm in May.

From 85 to 95% of the hills were infested. From 1 to 11 galls per hill were found; the average was 3. The hills averaged four panicles each.

The severe outbreak may have

occurred because 1) the village is adjacent to Prachinburi province where the insect was previously found at low levels; 2) the susceptible RD varieties are widely grown, supplying ample food; 3) rice is planted at high density by broadcasting; 4) irrigation throughout the year creates a suitable environment for gall midge reproduction; and 5) a high rate of fertilizer is applied.

Varietal reaction to rice @ midge, leaf rollers, and thrips

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In the Vaigai-Periyar river project of Tamil Nadu, the rice gall midge *Pachytiplosis oryzae* and the leaf roller *Chaphalocrosis medinalis* have become serious because of extensive and intensive cultivation of high yielding varieties.

The relative susceptibility or resistance of 85 prerelease cultures was assessed in a randomized field experiment with three replications at the Agricultural College and Research Institute Farm, Madurai, in 1975–76. Because a severe outbreak of the rice thrip *Baliothrips biformis* was noticed in the nursery stage, the varieties were also observed for their reactions to

Reaction of rice varieties to gall midge, leaf rollers, and thrips at Madurai, India.

Cultivar	Gall midge (% affected tillers)	Leaf roller (% affected leaves)	Thrips (n0./5 sweeps)
Most resistant varieties			
W. 1263	1.0	6.4	10.5
Kakatiya	6.8	1.8	5.0
CR 57-49-5	7.5	3.2	3.0
Isawarakora	1.5	3.4	7.0
PTB 10	7.4	3.7	3.5
PTB 21	7.8	4.6	2.5
Leang 152	8.0	6.2	2.5
CR 58-51	8.1	6.9	6.0
CR 95-R-14-1	8.2	7.8	9.5
CR 57-29 (non-pigmented)	8.8	8.1	3.5
CR 57-29 (pigmented)	9.6	9.6	—
Most susceptible varieties			
GMR 5	50.6	—	—
Cul. 4609	—	29.1	—
Co 36	—	—	66.5

the insect. Eleven varieties had fewer infestations by the three pests than did the others (see table). The variety

W. 1263 showed resistance to gall midge; Kakatiya, to leaf rollers; and PTB 21 and hang 152, to thrips.

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Deep water

The influence of varying depths and durations of submergence on the adaptability of rice varieties to low-lying waterlogged conditions in West Bengal, India

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Three hundred rice varieties were tested in eight specially constructed fields under shallow water, knee-deep water, semideep water, and deep water conditions at the Chinsurah station during the 1974–75 monsoon season. The experiments were conducted in randomized blocks with

two replications; each plot was 7 × 3 m. The soil was clay loam with a pH of 6.9. No manure was applied. The figure shows the extent of adaptability of promising low-lying varieties to varying waterlogged situations together with method of sowing, growth duration, and grain yield.

The findings suggest that Achra 108/1, CNL 214, and CNL 231 have a maximum degree of ecological adaptability to varying waterlogged conditions and can be grown in shallow water, knee-deep water, and semideep water. Similarly, Patnai 23, Tilakkachari, Kumargore,

CNL 270, and NC 1281 are well adapted to shallow and knee-deep water. Pankaj, CNL 312, NC 678, OC 1393, IR442-2-58, Kalma, and Raghusail grew well only in shallow water. CNL 180, CNL 31, Chakia 59, and Jalamagna have moderate adaptability and were found suitable for knee-deep and semideep water. Varieties such as CNDW 13, CNDW 395, Jaladhi 1 and Jaladhi 2 show great ecological adaptability to the greatest depth and duration of submergence; they can grow in both semideep and deep water. Typical floating rice varieties such as

Extent of adaptation (indicated by arrows) of rice varieties and their yield potentials at varying depths and durations of waterlogged situations at vegetative and reproductive stages under direct-sown and transplanted conditions. West Bengal, India.

CNDW 332, CNDW 326, Jaisuria, CNDW 325, and CNDW 327 are only suitable for deep-water condition.

The results indicate that the genetic potential of individual varieties determines the ability to adjust to varying depths and durations of submergence under waterlogged conditions. Therefore, those traits can be introduced into improved varieties with greater yield potential. The figure gives information on varietal suitability for different low-lying, waterlogged situations. Grain characteristics of the promising varieties are available by contacting the authors.

Breeding for deep-water conditions

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A breeding program to develop varieties suitable for deep-water conditions was initiated at the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad. Selections from the F₃ of the cross Rp 31-49-2 (short statured)/Leb Mue Nahng (tall, deep water-tolerant) — originally selected at AICRIP headquarters — were tested at the Deep Water Rice Research Station, Chagraghat, at a water depth of 70–80 cm for 1 month. On the basis of tolerance, 114 single-plant selections were made and further screened at Hyderabad, along with IRRI materials. Two sets of 100 of each entry were sown in four earthen pots. In the first set, 10-day-old seedlings remained submerged for 1 week in the drain at a water level of 150 cm. The percentage of seedlings that survived and their growth (in centimeters per day) during submergence were recorded. In the second set, 30-day-old seedlings were kept submerged. The performance of promising lines is summarized in the table.

The performance of promising lines screened for deep-water conditions. All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, India.

Designation	Cross	Seedlings submerged for 1 wk			
		10-day-old		30-day-old	
		survival (%)	Growth during submergence (cm/day)	Survival (%)	Growth during submergence (cm/day)
6204325	NP 31-49-2/ Leb Mue Nahng	94	2.9	91	2.9
6204314		81	2.4	90	3.3
6204435		90	0.4	87	3.1
KLG 6987-44-1	IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey	100	2.5	85	2.5
NP 31-492 (parent)	1 NP/Sigadis	0	0.0	41	0.6
Leb Mue Nahng	—	66	2.5	90	3.7